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**PROBLEMS OF STATE REGULATION IN SPHERE OF ASSESSING THE
 CREDITWORTHINESS OF BORROWERS AND THEIR IMPACT ON EFFICIENCY
 OF CREDIT MARKET**

The relevance of the study is driven by the growing structural imbalances in the domestic credit market, rooted in the mismatch between the existing regulatory paradigm and the realities of the digital economy. The article identifies key systemic problems of state regulation in assessing borrowers' creditworthiness. These include legal uncertainty in using alternative data and artificial intelligence algorithms, as well as the inadaptability of regulations for non-standard borrower categories (SMEs, self-employed, freelancers). The methodological basis comprises comparative legal analysis of the regulatory framework, a systems approach, and methods of economic analysis. It is proven that existing regulation has transformed from an infrastructural element into a source of constraints, reducing the allocative, operational, and innovative efficiency of the market. The consequence is chronic underfunding of key economic segments, distortion of competition, and increased systemic risks. In conclusion, the necessity of transitioning to a new, outcome-oriented and technologically neutral regulatory paradigm is substantiated. Specific strategic directions for its formation are proposed, including creating an «open finance» ecosystem, implementing regulatory «sandbox» institutions and a National Model Validation Center, and establishing a legal framework for algorithmic systems.

Keywords: creditworthiness, state regulation, credit market, machine learning, alternative data, non-standard borrowers, digital footprint, artificial intelligence (AI), financial technologies, regulatory paradigm.

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» [9], () » [12], 27.07.2006 152- « [11]. 21.12.2013 353- « 30.12.2004 218- « » [10], [1, 13], [3, 4, 15].

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- 1. 156/ // . — 2025. — . — 48 .
- 2. — 3- : / , 2021. — 424 . — ISBN 978-5-534-15075-9.
- 3. 2023-2025
// « » — URL: www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_517367/df08fa7552b11b107e5e8c981a38303da81f229e/ (:01.09.2025).
- 4. / // . — 2024. — 6-2. — . 312-316. — DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12621417. — EDN EHJLKI.
- 5. / // . — 2021. — 3(84). — . 91-100. — DOI 10.37493/2307-907X.2021.3.12. — EDN WPUVLR.
- 6. / // . — 2019. — 8(46). — . 43-48. — EDN QKCSEC.
- 7. / // . — 2019. — 7. — . 410-413. — EDN MKNXYZ.
- 8. 31.07.2025 289- // « » — URL: publication.pravo.gov.ru/Document/View/0001202507310020 (:01.09.2025).
- 9. : 30.12.2004 218- // « » — URL: base.garant.ru/12138288/ (:01.09.2025).
- 10. : 27.07.2006 152- // « » — URL: base.garant.ru/12148567/ (:01.09.2025).
- 11. 06.08.2015 483- // . — URL: www.cbr.ru/faq_ufr/dbrnfaq/doc/?number=483-%D0%9F (:01.09.2025).
- 12. () : 21.12.2013 353- // « » — URL: base.garant.ru/70544866/ (:01.09.2025).
- 13. 2027 2028 (, 2025) // . — URL: www.cbr.ru/about_br/publ/ondkp/on_2026_2028/ (:01.09.2025).
- 14. 590- () ;
)// . — URL: www.cbr.ru/Queries/UniDbQuery/File/90134/2760 (:01.09.2025).

